

Hi [interviewee's name], thank you for taking the time to speak with me today and participate in this study. My name is [interviewer's name].

The purpose of our discussion is to understand your experiences in using resources for supporting learning and implementations in software engineering. This interview will take around 1 hour. Before we begin the questions, I request you to kindly turn your cell phone to silent to avoid any distractions. [wait 30 seconds]

I'll be reading from a script to be consistent with all the participants in the study. Please feel free to take your time with answers - there are no right or wrong responses, I'm just interested in understanding your perspectives and experiences.

Also, I would like to audio record this interview with your permission, to ensure I accurately capture our conversation. The recording will only be used for analysis related to this study and all identifiable data will be kept confidential. Is it okay to record?

[Start recording on zoom]

Warm up....

So let's get started.

1. What resources do you like to use for learning software engineering?
 1. Why do you prefer those resources?
 2. What makes them most helpful for your learning?

As you mentioned in the [recruitment] survey that you've used generative AI during the SE courses, today we want to know about the experiences you had using genAI.

(Learning Concepts)

The first one, we will talk about your experiences when you used genAI to learn something in SE? I request you to open up conversations at your end before we start. [Wait till they open]

1. What genAI tools did you use?
2. Why did you use it?
3. What were you trying to learn?
 - a. What did you expect when you decided to use it?
 - b. How helpful was [genAI] for this case?
 - c. What difficulties did you face while using it?
 - d. How well could you learn these concepts using [genAI]?
4. Can you walk me through the process of using [genAI] for this case?
(If they mention they combined with other sources)
 - a. Why did you use [resource]?
 - b. How did you use it?
 - c. What did you do when there was a conflict between [genAI] and [resource]? Where did this happen most?

(Implementing solutions)

Now, the second experience, could you share an instance where you used genAI for software implementations or for projects/exercise? Once again, I request you to open up conversations at your end before we start. [Wait till they open]

1. What genAI tools did you use?
2. Why did you use it?
3. How well did it help?
4. What issues did you come across in the process using [genAI]?
5. How did you verify [genAI]'s responses?
 - a. How did you assess its quality and correctness?
 - b. What steps did you take to proceed when it was not helpful? (Optional)

(Overall experiences)

Lastly, let's talk about your overall experiences so far with [mentioned genAI's].

1. How long have you been using it?
2. What were the different issues you faced in using [genAI] for software engineering?
 - a. How did this [issue] impact?
 - b. How did you deal with it?
3. What were the gaps in using [genAI] for SE?
 - a. What didn't genAI cover well?
 - b. What do you think genAI tools could do better to support your needs?
4. How do you plan to use it in the future?

Close-up

4. Do you have any additional thoughts or feedback that you want to add about your experiences in using [genAI] for software engineering?

[Stop Recording]
